

Process Mining Meets Model Learning: Discovering Deterministic Finite State Automata for Business Process Analysis

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1. Experiments

Here follows the results of the experiments involving the computation of precision and generalization on the DFAs discovered from the synthetic logs (i.e., generated with MDL, RPNI, EDSM and L* algorithms).

*Fully documented templates are available in the elsarticle package on CTAN.
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Table 1: Precision₊@*k* of the DFAs generated with MDL

Log (ℓ)	$k = 1$	t	$k = 2$	t	$k = 3$	t
log_3_10	0.290	5s	0.045	3s	0.006	4s
log_3_15	0.250	3s	0.024	4s	0.002	23s
log_3_20	0.240	3s	0.016	4s	0.001	30s
log_3_25	0.402	3s	0.054	5s	0.004	1m10s
log_3_30	0.372	3s	0.045	6s	0.004	1m47s
log_5_10	0.250	3s	0.026	4s	0.002	14s
log_5_15	0.287	3s	0.027	4s	0.002	55s
log_5_20	0.370	5s	0.039	8s	0.003	1m35s
log_5_25	0.421	5s	0.045	15s	0.003	1m53s
log_5_30	0.501	3s	0.063	8s	0.004	1m48s
log_7_15	0.193	2s	0.016	3s	0.001	9s
log_7_20	0.458	3s	0.046	6s	0.003	1m5s
log_7_25	0.411	3s	0.038	7s	0.002	1m20s
log_7_30	0.569	3s	0.069	8s	0.004	1m38s
log_10_20	0.372	3s	0.032	5s	0.002	34s
log_10_25	0.461	3s	0.042	7s	0.003	1m25s
log_10_30	0.381	3s	0.030	6s	0.002	1m1s

Table 2: Precision₊@*k* and Precision₋@*k* of the DFAs generated with RPNI

(a) Precision ₊ @ <i>k</i>							(b) Precision ₋ @ <i>k</i>						
Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>	Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>
log_3_10	0.193	3s	0.025	3s	0.003	5s	log_3_10	0.149	5s	0.014	3s	0.001	6s
log_3_15	0.233	3s	0.022	4s	0.002	26s	log_3_15	0.198	3s	0.016	4s	0.001	26s
log_3_20	0.216	3s	0.019	5s	0.001	37s	log_3_20	0.210	4s	0.019	5s	0.001	49s
log_3_25	0.370	3s	0.049	5s	0.004	38s	log_3_25	0.415	3s	0.052	6s	0.004	56s
log_3_30	0.338	3s	0.039	5s	0.003	58s	log_3_30	0.364	3s	0.039	6s	0.003	1m5s
log_5_10	0.246	3s	0.026	4s	0.002	10s	log_5_10	0.196	3s	0.017	4s	0.001	13s
log_5_15	0.274	3s	0.025	5s	0.002	31s	log_5_15	0.239	3s	0.021	5s	0.001	33s
log_5_20	0.292	3s	0.027	6s	0.002	60s	log_5_20	0.288	3s	0.029	6s	0.002	1m4s
log_5_25	0.428	3s	0.047	8s	0.003	1m33s	log_5_25	0.436	3s	0.050	8s	0.003	3m22s
log_5_30	0.476	3s	0.058	9s	0.004	2m8s	log_5_30	0.517	4s	0.062	16s	0.004	5m11s
log_7_15	0.148	4s	0.012	4s	0.001	15s	log_7_15	0.285	3s	0.025	5s	0.002	1m17s
log_7_20	0.416	3s	0.041	7s	0.003	1m15s	log_7_20	0.348	3s	0.032	6s	0.002	2m34s
log_7_25	0.416	3s	0.040	7s	0.003	1m22s	log_7_25	0.517	3s	0.057	11s	0.004	4m37s
log_7_30	0.512	3s	0.060	9s	0.004	2m1s	log_7_30	0.467	4s	0.054	14s	0.004	4m16s
log_10_20	0.318	3s	0.025	6s	0.001	50s	log_10_20	0.334	4s	0.028	8s	0.002	2m6s
log_10_25	0.464	3s	0.044	7s	0.003	1m27s	log_10_25	0.588	4s	0.060	16s	0.004	4m53s
log_10_30	0.383	3s	0.031	6s	0.002	1m3s	log_10_30	0.613	3s	0.068	17s	0.004	5m34s

Table 3: Precision₊@*k* and Precision₋@*k* of the DFAs generated with EDSM

(a) Precision ₊ @ <i>k</i>							(b) Precision ₋ @ <i>k</i>						
Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>	Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>
log_3_10	0.191	3s	0.023	3s	0.002	5s	log_3_10	0.149	3s	0.014	3s	0.001	7s
log_3_15	0.230	3s	0.022	4s	0.002	25s	log_3_15	0.198	3s	0.016	5s	0.001	49s
log_3_20	0.219	3s	0.019	5s	0.001	36s	log_3_20	0.210	4s	0.019	6s	0.001	1m43s
log_3_25	0.361	3s	0.049	5s	0.004	36s	log_3_25	0.415	3s	0.052	6s	0.004	2m4s
log_3_30	0.339	3s	0.040	6s	0.003	54s	log_3_30	0.364	3s	0.039	6s	0.003	2m22s
log_5_10	0.245	3s	0.026	3s	0.002	11s	log_5_10	0.196	3s	0.017	3s	0.001	21s
log_5_15	0.267	3s	0.023	5s	0.002	31s	log_5_15	0.239	4s	0.021	6s	0.001	1m8s
log_5_20	0.287	3s	0.027	6s	0.002	59s	log_5_20	0.288	4s	0.029	8s	0.002	2m18s
log_5_25	0.424	3s	0.046	8s	0.003	1m38s	log_5_25	0.436	4s	0.050	14s	0.003	4m10s
log_5_30	0.477	4s	0.057	11s	0.004	2m34s	log_5_30	0.517	4s	0.062	17s	0.004	4m59s
log_7_15	0.147	3s	0.011	4s	0.001	15s	log_7_15	0.285	4s	0.025	5s	0.002	1m14s
log_7_20	0.416	3s	0.041	8s	0.003	1m27s	log_7_20	0.347	4s	0.032	9s	0.002	2m27s
log_7_25	0.414	3s	0.040	7s	0.003	1m24s	log_7_25	0.517	4s	0.057	14s	0.004	4m39s
log_7_30	0.514	4s	0.060	10s	0.004	2m11s	log_7_30	0.467	4s	0.054	13s	0.004	4m21s
log_10_20	0.322	3s	0.025	6s	0.002	54s	log_10_20	0.334	4s	0.028	7s	0.002	2m8s
log_10_25	0.465	3s	0.044	8s	0.003	1m32s	log_10_25	0.588	4s	0.060	14s	0.004	4m53s
log_10_30	0.383	3s	0.031	7s	0.002	1m9s	log_10_30	0.613	4s	0.068	17s	0.004	5m27s

Table 4: Precision₊@*k* and Precision₋@*k* of the DFAs generated with L*

(a) Precision ₊ @ <i>k</i>							(b) Precision ₋ @ <i>k</i>						
Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>	Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>
log_3.10	0.173	2s	0.018	3s	0.002	8s	log_3.10	0.157	3s	0.015	4s	0.001	8s
log_3.15	0.222	4s	0.020	7s	0.001	1m2s	log_3.15	0.189	6s	0.017	6s	0.001	6s
log_3.20	0.214	6s	0.018	11s	0.001	2m1s	log_3.20	0.218	8s	0.020	19s	0.001	3m41s
log_3.25	0.353	10s	0.044	21s	0.003	3m30s	log_3.25	0.427	16s	0.056	33s	0.005	3m20s
log_3.30	0.330	10s	0.037	21s	0.003	3m44s	log_3.30	0.383	13s	0.041	21s	0.003	2m56s
log_5.10	0.223	3s	0.020	4s	0.001	23s	log_5.10	0.210	4s	0.025	4s	0.001	4s
log_5.15	0.267	5s	0.023	8s	0.001	1m26s	log_5.15	0.247	6s	0.022	10s	0.001	1m11s
log_5.20	0.288	7s	0.026	16s	0.002	3m11s	log_5.20	0.299	10s	0.030	17s	0.002	3m54s
log_5.25	0.421	11s	0.045	31s	0.003	6m48s	log_5.25	0.449	24s	0.052	52s	0.003	10m42s
log_5.30	0.477	18s	0.057	49s	0.004	20m28s	log_5.30	0.470	28s	0.058	59s	0.003	11m34s
log_7.15	0.142	11s	0.009	13s	0.001	2m3s	log_7.15	0.293	6s	0.026	13s	0.002	2m23s
log_7.20	0.408	14s	0.039	45s	0.002	7m4s	log_7.20	0.359	15s	0.034	31s	0.002	5m25s
log_7.25	0.411	30s	0.039	1m28s	0.002	11m12s	log_7.25	0.532	32s	0.061	1m13s	0.004	10m24s
log_7.30	0.508	16s	0.058	42s	0.004	9m12s	log_7.30	0.479	30s	0.057	1m11s	0.004	13m47s
log_10.20	0.316	6s	0.024	14s	0.001	2m48s	log_10.20	0.346	14s	0.030	27s	0.001	4m30s
log_10.25	0.461	14s	0.042	40s	0.003	8m25s	log_10.25	0.601	29s	0.063	1m9s	0.004	12m11s
log_10.30	0.380	18s	0.030	49s	0.002	10m33s	log_10.30	0.628	16s	0.073	42s	0.005	12m9s

Table 5: Generalization₊@*k* of the DFAs generated with MDL

(a) Generalization₊@*k*

Log (ℓ)	$k = 1$	t	$k = 2$	t	$k = 3$	t
log_3_10	0.950	12s	0.920	12s	0.910	13s
log_3_15	0.956	12s	0.927	12s	0.871	20s
log_3_20	0.962	12s	0.925	12s	0.916	22s
log_3_25	0.967	12s	0.940	12s	0.919	20s
log_3_30	0.970	11s	0.950	13s	0.941	22s
log_5_10	0.954	12s	0.907	12s	0.867	16s
log_5_15	0.962	12s	0.933	12s	0.838	22s
log_5_20	0.984	12s	0.960	13s	0.940	22s
log_5_25	0.990	12s	0.955	13s	0.969	34s
log_5_30	0.991	11s	0.985	14s	0.983	40s
log_7_15	0.975	12s	0.960	13s	0.943	18s
log_7_20	0.968	13s	0.993	13s	0.990	29s
log_7_25	0.990	12s	1.0	21s	1.0	38s
log_7_30	1.0	13s	1.0	14s	1.0	37s
log_10_20	0.995	13s	0.980	14s	0.984	25s
log_10_25	0.984	12s	0.959	13s	0.945	33s
log_10_30	0.993	12s	0.980	32s	0.972	32s

Table 6: Generalization₊@*k* and Generalization₋@*k* of the DFAs generated with RPNI

(a) Generalization ₊ @ <i>k</i>							(b) Generalization ₋ @ <i>k</i>						
Log (ℓ)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>	Log (ℓ)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>
log_3_10	0.954	13s	0.909	21s	0.865	23s	log_3_10	1.0	21s	1.0	21s	1.0	26s
log_3_15	0.975	23s	0.906	22s	0.871	40s	log_3_15	1.0	20s	1.0	21s	1.0	42s
log_3_20	0.971	25s	0.930	26s	0.868	44s	log_3_20	1.0	22s	1.0	45s	1.0	1m
log_3_25	0.997	23s	0.977	25s	0.987	47s	log_3_25	1.0	22s	1.0	24s	1.0	48s
log_3_30	1.0	27s	1.0	27s	0.989	57s	log_3_30	1.0	20s	1.0	22s	1.0	56s
log_5_10	0.967	24s	0.870	25s	0.907	33s	log_5_10	1.0	20s	1.0	21s	1.0	32s
log_5_15	0.970	25s	0.962	27s	0.933	48s	log_5_15	1.0	15s	1.0	12s	1.0	30s
log_5_20	0.996	26s	0.978	27s	0.979	1m8s	log_5_20	1.0	12s	1.0	14s	1.0	40s
log_5_25	1.0	26s	0.992	30s	0.972	1m25s	log_5_25	1.0	12s	1.0	14s	1.0	52s
log_5_30	0.997	25s	0.993	28s	0.991	1m40s	log_5_30	1.0	12s	1.0	15s	1.0	58s
log_7_15	0.975	23s	0.960	26s	0.928	44s	log_7_15	1.0	12s	1.0	13s	1.0	30s
log_7_20	0.993	25s	0.987	26s	0.973	1m7s	log_7_20	1.0	19s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m1s
log_7_25	0.988	25s	0.981	27s	0.980	1m24s	log_7_25	1.0	21s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m17s
log_7_30	1.0	25s	0.995	27s	0.993	1m30s	log_7_30	1.0	21s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m12s
log_10_20	1.0	26s	0.985	28s	0.984	1m5s	log_10_20	1.0	21s	1.0	22s	1.0	55s
log_10_25	1.0	25s	0.997	28s	0.970	1m22s	log_10_25	1.0	21s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m12s
log_10_30	1.0	29s	0.990	29s	0.990	1m15s	log_10_30	1.0	21s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m15s

Table 7: Generalization₊@ k and Generalization₋@ k of the DFAs generated with EDSM

(a) Generalization ₊ @ k							(b) Generalization ₋ @ k						
Log (ℓ)	$k = 1$	t	$k = 2$	t	$k = 3$	t	Log (ℓ)	$k = 1$	t	$k = 2$	t	$k = 3$	t
log_3_10	0.963	21s	0.920	21s	0.901	22s	log_3_10	1.0	21s	1.0	21s	1.0	25s
log_3_15	0.975	21s	0.933	22s	0.928	21s	log_3_15	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	42s
log_3_20	0.943	12s	0.960	13s	0.837	23s	log_3_20	1.0	21s	1.0	22s	1.0	54s
log_3_25	1.0	13s	0.993	13s	0.983	23s	log_3_25	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	49s
log_3_30	0.997	13s	0.997	13s	1.0	28s	log_3_30	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	57s
log_5_10	0.957	12s	0.883	12s	0.859	16s	log_5_10	1.0	21s	1.0	22s	1.0	34s
log_5_15	0.958	12s	0.968	13s	0.945	23s	log_5_15	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	46s
log_5_20	0.993	12s	0.988	13s	0.960	30s	log_5_20	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	1m
log_5_25	0.995	13s	0.987	14s	0.988	39s	log_5_25	1.0	23s	1.0	24s	1.0	1m12s
log_5_30	0.998	14s	0.989	16s	0.994	48s	log_5_30	1.0	24s	1.0	27s	1.0	1m26s
log_7_15	0.975	12s	0.987	12s	0.914	21s	log_7_15	1.0	21s	1.0	22s	1.0	44s
log_7_20	0.990	13s	0.987	16s	0.961	40s	log_7_20	1.0	22s	1.0	24s	1.0	1m2s
log_7_25	0.997	15s	0.985	17s	0.978	42s	log_7_25	1.0	22s	1.0	25s	1.0	1m17s
log_7_30	1.0	16s	1.0	17s	0.993	49s	log_7_30	1.0	23s	1.0	26s	1.0	1m19s
log_10_20	0.990	14s	1.0	15s	0.968	35s	log_10_20	1.0	22s	1.0	23s	1.0	55s
log_10_25	0.992	15s	0.977	17s	0.975	44s	log_10_25	1.0	22s	1.0	25s	1.0	1m15s
log_10_30	0.996	15s	0.990	16s	0.986	40s	log_10_30	1.0	22s	1.0	24s	1.0	1m20s

Table 8: Generalization₊@*k* and Generalization₋@*k* of the DFAs generated with L*

(a) Generalization ₊ @ <i>k</i>							(b) Generalization ₋ @ <i>k</i>						
Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>	Log (<i>ℓ</i>)	<i>k</i> = 1	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 2	<i>t</i>	<i>k</i> = 3	<i>t</i>
log_3.10	1.0	14s	1.0	15s	1.0	27s	log_3.10	0.850	14s	0.701	15s	0.605	26s
log_3.15	1.0	21s	1.0	28s	1.0	2m22s	log_3.15	0.806	21s	0.659	25s	0.621	1m4s
log_3.20	1.0	29s	1.0	42s	1.0	4m55s	log_3.20	0.982	30s	0.976	40s	0.975	4m5s
log_3.25	1.0	43s	1.0	1m5s	1.0	6m49s	log_3.25	0.981	44s	0.973	1m	0.972	5m26s
log_3.30	1.0	46s	1.0	1m10s	1.0	8m21s	log_3.30	0.998	45s	0.987	1m5s	0.984	7m24s
log_5.10	1.0	17s	1.0	20s	1.0	1m1s	log_5.10	0.945	21s	0.833	23s	0.837	44s
log_5.15	1.0	27s	1.0	36s	1.0	3m7s	log_5.15	0.962	31s	0.933	35s	0.928	2m38s
log_5.20	1.0	39s	1.0	1m3s	1.0	7m23s	log_5.20	0.992	35s	0.958	50s	0.957	5m41s
log_5.25	1.0	55s	1.0	1m31s	1.0	13m52s	log_5.25	0.989	53s	0.976	1m22s	0.968	10m33s
log_5.30	1.0	1m14s	1.0	2m44s	1.0	26m20s	log_5.30	0.921	1m10s	0.685	1m30s	0.606	10m54s
log_7.15	1.0	27s	1.0	35s	1.0	3m5s	log_7.15	0.972	24s	0.957	31s	0.928	2m38s
log_7.20	1.0	43s	1.0	1m1s	1.0	7m51s	log_7.20	0.987	36s	0.960	52s	0.959	6m6s
log_7.25	1.0	1m12s	1.0	2m20s	1.0	22m6s	log_7.25	0.992	1m7s	0.966	1m54s	0.962	15m42s
log_7.30	1.0	1m13s	1.0	2m18s	1.0	25m37s	log_7.30	0.985	1m3s	0.975	1m42s	0.965	13m54s
log_10.20	1.0	1m27s	1.0	2m17s	1.0	14m17s	log_10.20	0.976	32s	0.950	46s	0.958	5m1s
log_10.25	1.0	2m16s	1.0	4m48s	1.0	20m45s	log_10.25	0.985	1m	0.969	1m39s	0.968	13m22s
log_10.30	1.0	1m16s	1.0	2m29s	1.0	33m52s	log_10.30	0.990	1m14s	0.972	2m9s	0.969	19m13s